

Deliverable 2.4: Active participation at international and national clinically oriented conference

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Basic information

Project title	Strategies to strengthen scientific excellence and innovation capacity for early diagnosis of gastrointestinal cancers
Project acronym	VISION
Call	H2020-WIDESPREAD-2018-2020
Topic	WIDESPREAD-03-2018
Project type	Coordination and Supporting Action (CSA)
Grant Agreement No.	857381
Nature	R (Document, report - excluding the periodic and final reports)
Dissemination level	PU (Public, fully open, e.g. web)

Executive summary

All consortium partners who take part in clinically orientated international and national meetings and conferences will promote the VISION project during oral and poster presentations. Either the Vision logo will be used in any presented work or the project will be referenced in the acknowledgements.

1 Description of work & main achievements

All members of the consortium that present their research at national or international conferences will promote the diffusion of the VISION project. All abstracts, poster presentations and lectures will include the project name and logo in the acknowledgement sections. The abstracts are published on the project website.

A summary of the main achievements are shown below:

Poster presentation: European Pancreatic Club meeting, Paris 1-3rd July 2020, (Virtual meeting):

Characterization of the germline and somatic mutation profile in familial pancreatic cancer reveals pathogenic germline variants and potentially druggable somatic mutations. Julie Earl, Maria E. Castillo, Emma Barreto, Mercedes Rodríguez-Garrote, Vanessa Pachón, Reyes Ferreiro, Maria Villamayor, David García-Seisdedos, Gloria Muñoz and Alfredo Carrato

The use of low intensity ultrasounds as a novel therapeutic tool in pancreatic cancer. Jesús Frutos Díaz-Alejo, Iciar González Gómez, Antonio Ramos Fernández, Luis M Rodríguez-Lorenzo, Alberto Pinto del Corral, Luis Hernández, Nieves Cubo Mateo, Vanessa Pachón Olmos, Cristian Perna and Julie Earl.

Presentations at online conference OpenTox Virtual Conference 2020, September 21-25 September, 2020:

Cell cultures in flow: approaches for in vivo-like safety screening. Yvonne Kohl, Thorsten Knoll, Margit Biehl, Michelle Hesler, Sarah Spring, Lena Gammel, Hagen von Briesen, Sylvia Wagner, Thomas Velten

Renal advanced in vitro models for nephrotoxicity determination. Monika Sramkova, Kristina Kopecka, Yvonne Kohl, Sarah Spring, Michelle Hesler, Thorsten Knoll, Alena Gabelova

2 Deviation from the workplan

The work plan has not changed, although the majority of conferences are now performed on-line due to the COVID crisis.

3 Conclusion

Due to the COVID crisis, the majority of conferences have been cancelled or been converted to virtual conferences. This has obviously affected our ability to promote the project efficiently, although we have been able to make some progress.